

VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY IN PATIENTS WITH NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE

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Abstract

Background: Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) is a growing health concern in Pakistan and globally, often coexisting with metabolic disorders. Emerging evidence suggests an association between vitamin D deficiency and NAFLD, potentially contributing to disease progression. This study aimed to determine the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and its associated factors in patients diagnosed with NAFLD.

Patients and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted over six months in the Department of Medicine, Liaquat University Hospital Hyderabad. A total of 130 adult patients (aged 20-60 years), diagnosed with NAFLD via ultrasound and meeting strict inclusion/exclusion criteria, were enrolled. Vitamin D deficiency was defined as serum vitamin D ≤ 20 ng/mL. Data on demographics, clinical features, comorbidities, lifestyle habits, and biochemical parameters were collected. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 22.0. Chi-square test was applied, and p -value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: Vitamin D deficiency was observed in 93 (71.5%) NAFLD patients. Significant associations were found with obesity ($p < 0.001$), diabetes mellitus ($p = 0.006$), hyperlipidemia ($p = 0.02$), anemia ($p = 0.003$), junk food consumption ($p < 0.001$), low sun exposure ($p < 0.001$), and low AST/ALT ratio ($p < 0.001$). No statistically significant relationship was found with gender, marital status, or smoking status.

Conclusion: Vitamin D deficiency is highly prevalent among patients with NAFLD and is significantly associated with several modifiable metabolic and lifestyle factors. These findings highlight the need for early screening and management of vitamin D status in NAFLD patients to potentially improve clinical outcomes and halt disease progression.

INTRODUCTION

Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) represents a broad spectrum of liver conditions

characterized by excess fat accumulation in the liver in individuals who consume little to no

alcohol. It is identified both clinically and histologically, primarily affecting patients without a significant history of alcohol intake [1]. The disease encompasses a range of liver abnormalities from simple steatosis (Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver or NAFL), which lacks signs of inflammation, to Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis (NASH), where fat accumulation is accompanied by inflammation and varying degrees of fibrosis [2-4].

The pathophysiology of NAFLD is complex and multifactorial. The "multiple-hit" hypothesis offers a more comprehensive understanding of its development, suggesting that various metabolic insults such as insulin resistance, oxidative stress, and inflammatory cytokines collectively contribute to liver damage [5-7]. Contrary to earlier beliefs, recent research indicates that the progression of NAFLD is not always a stepwise process. Not all patients with simple steatosis will inevitably advance to NASH or cirrhosis. The disease is often seen as a hepatic manifestation of broader metabolic dysfunction, particularly in individuals with type 2 diabetes and dyslipidemia [8, 9].

Vitamin D, a fat-soluble secosteroid, has gained attention for its potential role in a wide range of diseases, including autoimmune disorders, cardiovascular conditions, cancers, chronic inflammation, and liver diseases. Recent studies have increasingly focused on the relationship between vitamin D status and NAFLD [10]. Although the exact mechanisms are not fully understood, vitamin D is believed to exert anti-inflammatory and anti-fibrotic effects on hepatic stellate cells, which play a key role in liver fibrosis [11, 12].

Experimental evidence suggests that vitamin D helps counteract insulin resistance in both liver and peripheral tissues, thereby potentially reducing intrahepatic fat deposition a major contributor to NAFLD development [13]. For instance, Konstantakis et al. demonstrated in an animal model that vitamin D suppresses hepatic stellate cell proliferation, indicating its potential anti-fibrotic properties [14]. Similarly, a large database review by Liangpunsakul et al. involving over 6,000 individuals revealed that patients with

unexplained elevated ALT levels had significantly lower vitamin D concentrations compared to controls [15].

Several studies have reported varying prevalence rates of vitamin D deficiency among NAFLD patients: 70% in the study by Gad AI et al., 32% in Yodoshi T et al., and 45% in Kumar M et al. [16-18]. Given the shared risk factors such as obesity, poor dietary habits, and a sedentary lifestyle, it is biologically plausible that vitamin D deficiency could contribute to the pathogenesis and progression of NAFLD.

In light of these associations, this study was designed to assess the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among adult patients diagnosed with NAFLD at Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad. Understanding the magnitude of this deficiency may guide clinical decisions and offer a basis for targeted interventions aimed at improving liver and metabolic health.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted over a six-month (July 1st, 2024 to Dec 31, 2024) period in the Department of Medicine at Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad. Prior to initiation, the study protocol received approval from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP), and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Patients presenting to the outpatient department (OPD) with complaints of abdominal discomfort such as pain or fullness, along with symptoms including nausea, vomiting, loss of appetite, fatigue, or dyspepsia persisting for six weeks or more, were clinically evaluated. Those subsequently diagnosed with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) were admitted to the medical ward and enrolled consecutively into the study using non-probability sampling.

The sample size was calculated based on an anticipated prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in NAFLD patients of 32%, [15] with a margin of error set at 8%, resulting in a total of 130 patients.

NAFLD diagnosis was confirmed through abdominal ultrasonography performed by an experienced sonologist (≥ 5 years' experience).

Imaging findings considered diagnostic included increased hepatic echogenicity ("bright liver"), blurring of vascular structures, and narrowing of hepatic venous lumens. Patients with a history of alcohol consumption or use of medications known to cause hepatic steatosis within the past six weeks were excluded based on detailed clinical history. Vitamin D deficiency was defined as serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels ≤ 20 ng/mL.

Inclusion criteria encompassed adults aged 20 to 60 years of either gender, with persistent gastrointestinal symptoms for ≥ 6 weeks and a confirmed diagnosis of NAFLD for at least one month.

Exclusion criteria included individuals currently taking lipid-lowering agents, vitamin D or multivitamin supplements, or anti-obesity medications; pregnant or lactating women; and patients with known endocrine or systemic disorders such as hypothyroidism, malignancies (e.g., gastric or colonic cancer), malabsorption syndromes, parathyroid abnormalities, liver cirrhosis, or chronic kidney disease. Those with a history of alcohol use were also excluded to rule out alcoholic liver disease.

Blood samples (2cc) were drawn via aseptic technique using sterilized 5cc syringes and sent to the institutional laboratory for serum vitamin D estimation. Laboratory tests were conducted by a senior pathologist with more than five years of experience. Data was collected using a structured, pre-designed proforma. All costs related to investigations and procedures were borne by the principal investigator.

Patient evaluation included a thorough clinical history and physical examination. Vital signs such as blood pressure (measured with a sphygmomanometer), radial pulse, and body temperature (assessed using a mercury thermometer) were recorded. Abdominal examination was performed to check for tenderness, hepatosplenomegaly, or any other relevant findings. Anthropometric measurements were taken to calculate Body Mass Index (BMI) using the standard formula (weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared).

Important definitions:

Hypertension: Blood pressure $\geq 140/90$ mmHg at presentation.

Smoking: Defined as smoking ≥ 5 cigarettes/day for ≥ 1 year; ex-smokers were those who had quit for over one year; non-smokers had no history of tobacco use.

Hyperlipidemia: Presence of elevated cholesterol, triglycerides, or LDL, and/or low HDL levels.

Diabetes Mellitus: Diagnosis ≥ 1 year and/or random blood glucose ≥ 200 mg/dL.

Obesity: BMI ≥ 27.5 kg/m².

Anemia: Hemoglobin < 13 g/dL in males and < 12 g/dL in females.

Junk Food Consumption: Intake of fast food or processed foods on three or more days per week.

Vegetarian: Individuals who have abstained from eating meat or fish since birth.

Low AST/ALT Ratio: Defined as a serum AST to ALT ratio < 1 .

Educational Status: Categorized as illiterate, primary, middle, secondary, or higher education.

Marital Status: Classified as married, single, separated, or divorced.

Sunlight Exposure: Assessed as high or low based on seasonal and daily activity patterns.

Occupation: Grouped into housewives, employed, unemployed, or businessmen.

All data were analyzed using SPSS version 22.0. Descriptive statistics were used to calculate frequencies and percentages for categorical variables such as gender, place of residence, educational and marital status, sunlight exposure, occupation, and presence of comorbidities. Mean and standard deviation (SD) were computed for

quantitative variables including age and duration of NAFLD. Stratification was performed based on key demographic and clinical variables to assess their potential effect on the primary outcome (vitamin D deficiency). Post-stratification analysis was conducted using the Chi-square test or Fisher’s exact test as appropriate. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant, with a 95% confidence interval.

RESULTS:

Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants:

A total of 130 patients diagnosed with Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) were enrolled in the study. The mean age of participants was 43.6 ± 9.8 years, with 61 (46.9%) males and 69 (53.1%) females. The mean duration of NAFLD was 2.4 ± 1.1 years. Majority of patients were from urban areas (n=81, 62.3%), while 49 (37.7%) were from rural areas. Regarding education level, 32 (24.6%) were illiterate, 22 (16.9%) had primary education, 28 (21.5%) had completed middle school, 26 (20.0%) secondary, and 22 (16.9%) had higher education.

Marital and Occupational Status:

Most of the participants were married (n=110, 84.6%), while 20 (15.4%) were unmarried, separated or divorced. In terms of occupation, 58 (44.6%) were housewives, 34 (26.2%) were employed, 21 (16.2%) were unemployed, and 17 (13.1%) were businessmen.

Clinical and Lifestyle Characteristics:

Vitamin D deficiency was found in 93 (71.5%) of the NAFLD patients. Hypertension was present in 49 (37.7%) cases. Smoking was reported in 38 (29.2%) individuals. Hyperlipidemia was observed in 56 (43.1%) participants. Diabetes mellitus was present in 45 (34.6%). Obesity was present in 81 (62.3%). Anemia was diagnosed in 69 (53.1%) patients. Junk food consumption was observed in 75 (57.7%) individuals. Vegetarian diet was followed by 11 (8.5%) patients. Low AST/ALT ratio was identified in 72 (55.4%) patients. Low sun exposure was reported by 85 (65.4%) participants.

Table I: Stratification of Vitamin D Deficiency

Parameter	Total (n=130)	Vitamin D Deficient n (%)	p-value
Gender	Male (61) / Female (69)	41 (67.2%) / 52 (75.4%)	0.30
Residence	Urban (81) / Rural (49)	55 (67.9%) / 38 (77.6%)	0.21
Education	Illiterate vs Higher	28 (87.5%) / 12 (54.5%)	0.01*
Marital Status	Married (110) / Others (20)	80 (72.7%) / 13 (65.0%)	0.48
Sun Exposure	Low (85) / High (45)	71 (83.5%) / 22 (48.9%)	<0.001*
Occupation	Housewife (58) / Employed (34) / Others (38)	46 (79.3%) / 19 (55.9%) / 28 (73.7%)	0.04*
Hypertension	Yes (49) / No (81)	40 (81.6%) / 53 (65.4%)	0.05*
Smoking	Smoker (38) / Non-smoker (92)	31 (81.6%) / 62 (67.4%)	0.11
Hyperlipidemia	Yes (56) / No (74)	46 (82.1%) / 47 (63.5%)	0.02*
Diabetes	Yes (45) / No (85)	39 (86.7%) / 54 (63.5%)	0.006*
Obesity	Yes (81) / No (49)	68 (84.0%) / 25 (51.0%)	<0.001*
Anemia	Yes (69) / No (61)	57 (82.6%) / 36 (59.0%)	0.003*

Parameter	Total (n=130)	Vitamin D Deficient n (%)	p-value
Junk Food Consumption	Yes (75) / No (55)	63 (84.0%) / 30 (54.5%)	<0.001*
Vegetarian	Yes (11) / No (119)	10 (90.9%) / 83 (69.7%)	0.14
Low AST/ALT Ratio	Yes (72) / No (58)	61 (84.7%) / 32 (55.2%)	<0.001*

*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

The vitamin D deficiency was highly prevalent (71.5%) among NAFLD patients.

Significant associations were found between Vitamin D deficiency and educational status ($p=0.01$), sun exposure ($p<0.001$), occupation ($p=0.04$), hyperlipidemia ($p=0.02$), diabetes ($p=0.006$), obesity ($p<0.001$), anemia ($p=0.003$), junk food consumption ($p<0.001$) and low AST/ALT ratio ($p<0.001$). No significant associations were observed with gender, residence, smoking, or marital status.

DISCUSSION: This cross-sectional descriptive study evaluated the frequency and associated factors of vitamin D deficiency among patients with Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) at Liaquat University Hospital, Hyderabad. The findings revealed a high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency (71.5%) among NAFLD patients, which aligns with previous literature suggesting a significant link between hypovitaminosis D and metabolic liver disorders. Vitamin D plays a crucial role not only in calcium-phosphate homeostasis but also in modulating inflammation, insulin resistance, and liver fibrosis – all key components in the pathogenesis of NAFLD. Our results are consistent with several international and regional studies. A study conducted by Barchetta et al. reported a prevalence of 65% vitamin D deficiency in NAFLD patients, supporting the metabolic implication of this micronutrient in hepatic steatosis progression [19]. Similarly, Eliades et al. and Targher et al. emphasized the inverse correlation between serum vitamin D levels and NAFLD severity [20, 21].

In the current study, we found that vitamin D deficiency was significantly more prevalent among patients with obesity, diabetes mellitus,

hyperlipidemia, and anemia. These associations reinforce the role of vitamin D in metabolic regulation. Obesity, particularly visceral adiposity, is known to reduce bioavailable vitamin D due to sequestration in adipose tissues, leading to reduced hepatic metabolism of vitamin D and increased risk of NAFLD [22]. Diabetes mellitus, another independent risk factor in our study, is thought to be aggravated by low vitamin D via its effects on pancreatic beta-cell function and insulin sensitivity [23].

Our findings also demonstrated a strong association between low sun exposure and vitamin D deficiency. This is expected in a region like Pakistan, where despite ample sunlight; cultural clothing, indoor lifestyles, and air pollution often limit effective UVB exposure. Education and occupation were also significantly associated, with illiterate individuals and housewives showing higher deficiency rates, possibly due to lack of awareness and restricted outdoor activity. These socioeconomic variables were similarly highlighted in a study by Ahmed et al., who found a higher risk of deficiency among females and those with lower education [24].

Interestingly, junk food consumption was also significantly linked with vitamin D deficiency. This dietary pattern, typically low in essential nutrients and high in trans fats, may exacerbate both hepatic fat accumulation and micronutrient insufficiency. The association of a low AST to ALT ratio with vitamin D deficiency suggests its potential utility as a biochemical marker of liver dysfunction severity, further reinforcing previous observations in the literature [25].

The lack of significant association with gender and smoking may be attributed to a relatively balanced gender distribution and underreporting of tobacco use, especially among females due to

social norms. However, other studies have reported mixed findings on these associations. The strengths of this study include strict exclusion criteria to rule out confounding liver conditions (such as viral hepatitis, cirrhosis, or alcoholism), and the consistent application of ultrasonography and laboratory analysis by experienced professionals. However, it is not without limitations. Being a single-center hospital-based study, the results may not be generalizable to the broader population. Additionally, factors such as parathyroid hormone levels, dietary vitamin D intake, and genetic polymorphisms were not assessed. This study highlights a high burden of vitamin D deficiency among NAFLD patients and its significant association with several modifiable metabolic and lifestyle factors. Early screening and correction of vitamin D deficiency may not only aid in improving hepatic outcomes but also address broader metabolic disturbances. Public health interventions targeting sun exposure, dietary habits, obesity, and educational outreach are warranted in such high-risk populations.

CONCLUSION: This study found a notably high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among NAFLD patients, with over 70% of participants affected. The deficiency was significantly associated with key modifiable risk factors, including obesity, diabetes mellitus, hyperlipidemia, anemia, dietary habits, and low sun exposure. These findings underline the importance of routine screening for vitamin D levels in patients with NAFLD, particularly those with co-existing metabolic conditions. Given the role of vitamin D in immune regulation, insulin sensitivity, and inflammation, addressing its deficiency may not only help in improving liver health but also reduce the risk of associated metabolic syndromes. Early nutritional interventions, lifestyle modifications including increased sun exposure, and supplementation could serve as effective strategies in the integrated management of NAFLD. Future longitudinal studies are recommended to explore the causal relationship between vitamin D deficiency and NAFLD progression, as well as the therapeutic potential of vitamin D supplementation in this population.

AUTHOR’S CONTRIBUTION:

Collection and acquisition of data & grammatical corrections	<i>Dr. Khadim Khoso</i>
Concept & design of study & proof read	<i>Dr. Abdul Ghani Rahimoon</i>
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	<i>Dr. Farheen Qadeer</i>
Revising critically and make it suitable for final format	<i>Dr. Rawal Majeed</i>
Acquisition of data and grammatical review	<i>Dr. Sanjha Sachal</i>
Drafting the article and finalizing the manuscript	<i>Dr. Zohaib Abbasi</i>
Revision of the manuscript	<i>Dr. Beenish Memon</i>
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